

Prof. dr iur. hab. Marcin Łysko,*
Associate Professor,
Faculty of Law, University of Białystok,
Republic of Poland

UDK: 351.74/.75:343.11(438)

UDK: 343.232(438)(091)

UDK: 364.654(438)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17949859

ADJUDICATION IN PETTY OFFENCES CASES IN THE POLISH PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC IN THE CONTEXT OF SOCIO-POLITICAL PROBLEMS IN THE POST-WAR PERIOD

Abstract: *This paper presents the practice of adjudicating petty offences in the People's Republic of Poland, where the adjudication in petty offence cases was misused as a means of political repression against people who were perceived to be the opponents of the communist system and as a means of resolving social problems stemming from the demoralisation of society and failures in the field of social education of young people. The adjudication in petty offence cases was supervised by the Ministry of Internal Affairs, which instituted solutions that treated adjudication boards (panels) as an instrument for exercising the current interests of the Ministry. In particular, those practices were often used during political crises. The most important solution was the concept of an alcohol and hooliganism-related misdemeanour, where the state of intoxication was treated as a relevant circumstance in deciding on the hooligan nature of a crime. The label "hooligan" was often attached to political opponents of the communist regime, individuals leading the so-called "parasitic" lifestyle, and people from the so-called social margin, such as alcohol addicts, beggars, prostitutes, vagrants, etc. Another basis for the repression of actual and fabricated opponents of the communist system was the wide application of expedite (summary) proceedings, where judges imposed severe fines. In case of the defendant's failure to pay, the imposed fine was immediately commuted into detention but this decision was not subject to the judicial control.*

Keywords: *adjudicating petty offences, People's Republic of Poland, Misdemeanours Code (1971), alcohol and hooliganism-related misdemeanours, expedite proceedings.*

* marcin.lysko@uwb.edu.pl, ORCID ID 0000-0002-2789-4679.

1. Introduction

This paper presents the practice of adjudication in petty offence cases in the People's Republic of Poland (1952-1989), where the communist authorities applied such practices for resolving the socio-political problems. The historical period of the People's Republic of Poland covers the period from 1944 to 1989, when Poland was ruled by communist authorities, under the substantial influence of the Soviet Union. The Communist Party, which governed Poland in an authoritarian way from the end of the Stalinist period in 1956, regarded law as a tool to protect the state and to repress the people who were perceived to be the communist system opponents. Another political aspect of the application of the law was the resolution of social problems resulting from the demoralisation of society caused by World War II and failures in the field of social education of young people (Łysko, 2014: 230). The practice of instrumental treatment of law also affected the adjudication in petty offences cases. The Polish Act on the Criminal and Administrative Jurisprudence of December 1951¹ was modelled upon the Soviet Union legislation. The reform of the Polish misdemeanour law system was based on the socialist idea of exerting an educational influence on the perpetrator, which ultimately resulted in abolishing the application the custodial sanctions. Imprisonment was replaced by the penalty of corrective labour, which was performed as a community service activity or entailed the offender's temporary employment at a state-owned workplace (Łysko, 2008: 149-150).

In line with the Soviet Union legislation, the Polish legislative act of December 1951 introduced boards (panels) for adjudicating in petty offence cases involving a social component. The adjudication boards were established in the local branches of state administration; thus, general guidelines on the penalty policy were issued by the Minister of Internal Affairs (Łysko, 2013: 319). Those guidelines typically had a repressive character because the Minister ordered the members of adjudication boards to intensify the restrictions. Under these guidelines, the perpetrators of serious offences were to be awarded severe penalties. As the judicial review on adjudication in petty offences was abolished, adjudication boards were separated from the judicial structures (Łysko, 2012: 250-253). Dependence on the state administration meant that the adjudication in petty offences was treated as a tool supporting the implementation of current state policy and as a means of resolving social problems resulting from the demoralisation of society caused by many years of German occupation and the communist authorities' neglect in the field of youth education.

¹ Ustawa o orzecznictwie karno-administracyjnym (The Act on the Criminal and Administrative Jurisprudence), *Dziennik Ustaw*/Journal of Laws 1951/66.

2. Adjudication in cases pertaining to compulsory delivery of agricultural products

During the Stalinist period (the first half of the 50s), peasants' were obliged to deliver a compulsory quota of agricultural products to the state authorities. In this period, peasants were subject to adjudication in petty offences for failure to perform the imposed obligation. The implementation of this provision in 1951 was aimed at subjecting farming to the principles of planned economy by its gradual collectivisation (Kaliński, 1995: 64). In view of the abysmal economic policy, the communist government tried to resolve the difficulties with providing supplies to cities by instituting administrative and penal repression on a large scale. For ideological reasons, the repression was primarily aimed at rich farmers who were treated as "enemies of the people" and imposed severe fines because the catalogue of penalties that the adjudication boards had at their disposal did not include the punishment of imprisonment. The imposed fines were not very efficient because farmers did not want to pay. In March 1953, the communist authorities responded by introducing custody as a substitute penalty in case the farmer failed to pay the fine. This solution was in conflict with the socialist idea of exerting an educational influence on the offender, as the idea underlying the misdemeanour law reform of December 1951 (Łysko, 2020: 204-205). The introduction of the substitute custodial penalty in case of failure to deliver the compulsory quota of agriculture products yielded good results as the farmers started fulfilling their obligations but the criminal policy in such cases became very repressive. In particular, severe restrictions were imposed in 1954 when over 103,000 people were fined for failure to deliver the compulsory supplies while 5,647 of them were imprisoned (Ministry of Interior Affairs I, 1955: 327).² In practice, adjudication boards applied severe punishments without thorough examination of each case, which led to multiple mistakes and suffering of the rural population. The victims of such practices of the adjudication boards were mainly small landowners and yeomen. The boards were particularly callous in punishing elderly people who were in severe financial plight or could not run their farms due to poor health conditions. There were also cases involving detention of the farmers' sons even though they did not perform any agricultural activities (Ministry of Interior Affairs I, 1954: 291-292).³ In 1955, when the first signs of the post-Stalinist "thaw" emerged, the system of adjudicating petty offences became less

² Analiza udziału orzecznictwa karno-administracyjnego w 1955 roku w realizacji planów dostaw obowiązkowych, Ministry of Internal Affairs I, sign. 11 + 2 (1955).

³ Analiza orzecznictwa karno-administracyjnego za okres IV kwartału 1954 r. z terenu województwa łódzkiego, Ministry of Internal Affairs I, sign. 526 (1954).

repressive. ‘Mechanical’ punishments were replaced by educational dialogues, aimed at convincing the offenders to deliver the supplies voluntarily. The scope of adjudication boards’ authority to impose the substitute penalty of detention was limited and boards were allowed to suspend the detention penalty due to economic and other life-related reasons. Thus, in 1955, there were only 345 farmers in prisons (Ministry of Interior Affairs II, 1955: 31-32).⁴ In 1956, when the government was headed by Wladyslaw Gomulka, the compulsory delivery of supplies was no longer treated as a political issue. The amount of the compulsory delivery was reduced and only administrative coercive measures were applied to those who failed to perform the duty. These measures were abolished in 1971 (Łysko, 2009: 213-214).

3. The Polish misdemeanour law system after the political breakthrough in 1956

After the political breakthrough from the Soviet Union in October 1956, the Polish misdemeanour law system became more repressive. In the opinion of communist authorities, the socialist idea of exerting educational influence on the perpetrator (which was the underlying principle in the adjudication of petty offences and the reform of December 1951) completely failed in the adjudication practice. Due to this idea, adjudication boards were deprived of the possibility to apply custodial sanctions. As a result, boards were often powerless when faced with offenders who had committed socially dangerous misdemeanours related to hooliganism or alcohol abuse (Łysko, 2008: 185-186). The escalation of hooliganism after 1956 was a consequence of demoralisation in the aftermath of the Second World War and the flawed system of educating youth in the post-war Poland. Most hooliganism offences were adjudicated by adjudication boards’ however, after the administrative boards were deprived of the possibility of impose the penalty of imprisonment in 1951, they could only impose fines or the corrective labour penalty against hooligans. These penalties were difficult to administer in a situation when the perpetrator of a misdemeanour had no permanent employment (Łysko, 2011: 28-281).

The conditions for imposing severe punishment for hooliganism-related misdemeanors were created by the Act on increasing Criminal Responsibility for Hooliganism, passed in May 1958.⁵ The penalty of detention (custo-

⁴ Notatka informacyjna dla Kolegium Ministerstwa Spraw Wewnętrznych o przebiegu orzecznictwa karno-administracyjnego w 1955 roku, Ministry of Internal Affairs II, sign. 6443 (1955).

⁵ Ustawa o zaostrzeniu odpowiedzialności karnej za chuligaństwo (Act on Increasing Criminal

dial sentence) was restored and the maximum fine was significantly increased. In cases of non-performance, the imposed fine could be converted into imprisonment, which ensured proper administration and service of punishment (Gubiński, 1977: 29-30). In the same year, the system of sanctions for misdemeanours was significantly changed by introducing principal novelties in the 1958 Act amending the Act on Criminal and Administrative Jurisprudence of 15th December 1951.⁶ The changes that were introduced in the amended 1958 Act had an adverse effect because the repressive tendencies were strengthened by limiting the educational element. By reintroducing detention and substitute custodial penalty, the catalogue of penalties became much more stringent. The penalty of corrective labour, which was ineffective in relation to offenders without a permanent place of residence and employment, was abolished (Łysko, 2014: 238-239).

The adjudication boards were entitled to impose a detention of up to 3 months in cases of misdemeanors that in practice constituted acts of hooliganism and included intoxication of the perpetrator.⁷ As a result of reintroducing the detention penalty, which had been abolished by the 1951 Act, the institute of referring the case to court proceedings was partially reinstated (Łysko 2013: 371-372). However, the judicial review still did not cover the detention penalty imposed as the result of conversion a fine that was not paid on time into a substitute custodial penalty. The adjudication boards had the discretionary authority to impose substitute custodial penalty because the amended 1958 Act on Criminal and Administrative Jurisprudence did not provide for any restrictions on the application of this penalty (Łysko, 2018: 180).

Guided by the assumption that the 'repressiveness' of the penal-administrative law system would be tightened, the amended 1958 Act increased the upper limit of maximum fines by half. This legal solution resulted in a significant increase in the substantive severity of penalties imposed for the most serious misdemeanours. The adjudication boards were deprived of the possibility to discontinue proceedings in case of a minor social harm caused by committed act, which ultimately implied an obligation to punish the pepe-

Responsibility for Hooliganism), *Dziennik Ustaw*, 1958/34.

⁶ Ustawa z dnia 2 grudnia 1958 r. o zmianie ustawy z dnia 15 grudnia 1951 r. o orzecznictwie karno-administracyjnym (the Act amending the Act on Criminal and Administrative Jurisprudence of 15th December 1951), *Dziennik Ustaw*, 1958/77).

⁷ These were the following misdemeanours: disturbing the public peace, violating the law and order regulations on conduct in public places, disturbing night-time rest, committing acts of indecency, and using indecent words. Detention may also have been ordered for disturbing public order or causing public umbrage in a state of intoxication (Bafia, 1959: 110).

trators of even the most minor misdemeanours each time. The only remaining relic of the educational character of adjudication was the penalty of reprimand, introduced instead of a warning, although it could not be imposed on the perpetrators of misdemeanours punishable by imprisonment (Łysko, 2014, 238-239).

4. Adjudication of petty offences as a means of combating negative social phenomena

From the perspective of state authorities, the 1958 Act was undoubtedly a success as it granted the adjudication boards the possibility to impose severe penalties which contributed to reducing the social problem of hooliganism and improving the general security in the country. According to the Ministry of the Internal Affairs guidelines, the adjudication boards primarily had to focus on punishing the perpetrators of socially dangerous alcoholism and hooliganism-related misdemeanours and minor offences against road safety (Wytyczne, 1960: 2).

In practice, the adjudication in petty offences was often used for imposing severe punishment on hooligans; yet, the pressure of the public opinion and government authorities on the adjudication bodies frequently resulted in hasty sentencing decisions and false classification of various misdemeanours as hooligan offences. The basic premise underlying hooliganism-related offences was that the illicit act was performed under the influence of alcohol. Given that the offenders of socially dangerous hooliganism-related misdemeanours were usually under the influence of alcohol or alcohol addicts at the time of committing the act, the term “alcoholism and hooliganism-related” offence was created in the adjudication practice. The Ministry of Internal Affairs was in charge of supervising the adjudication in petty offences. Thus, by combining the two types of misdemeanours (hooliganism and alcoholism-related ones), the adjudication in petty offences was aimed at combating another important social problem of post-war Poland – alcoholism (Łysko, 2009: 315).

The phenomenon of alcoholism, which was a consequence of society demoralization, grew into a social problem after 1956, when the governing power was taken by Władysław Gomułka. As the leader of Communist Party, Gomułka conducted an anti-alcoholism campaign mainly by means of repressive methods. Adjudication in petty offences played an important role in the policy of combating alcoholism, which was conducted on the basis of the anti-alcoholism law (Act on Combating Alcoholism) passed in 1959.⁸

⁸ Ustawa, z dnia 10 grudnia 1959 r. o zwalczaniu alkoholizmu (Act on Combating Alcoholism), *Dziennik Ustaw*, 1959/69.

This Act prescribed strict penalties of detention and fine for offences committed under the influence of alcohol (Łysko, 2020: 38-39). The repression of the perpetrators of this type of illegal offences was tightly connected with an anti-hooliganism campaign initiated by the authorities based on the premise that alcohol abuse was the cause of a vast majority of hooliganism acts. As many hooligans were alcohol addicts, they were detained for a maximum period of time and imposed high fines as a substitute penalty for detention. In relation to alcohol addicts, detention was practically used as an instrument of solitary confinement, which served to hide the deficiencies of the detoxification treatment of people addicted to alcohol (Łysko, 2011: 156-157).

In addition to imposing severe penalties on the perpetrators of “alcoholism and hooliganism-related” misdemeanours, the adjudication boards also served as a means for repressing people from the so-called social margin groups, considering that the law did not prescribe the punishment for pathological cases of prostitution, begging or vagrancy. Thus, on the basis of the legal construction of alcoholism and hooliganism-related offences, the people without a permanent place of residence and regular incomes were frequently awarded the detention penalty and substitute custodial penalty. Instead of making an attempt to prevent social problems such as drunkenness, prostitution, vagrancy or begging, Gomułka’s authorities resorted to an extensive criminal-administrative repression (Jakubowska-Hara, 2004: 56-57).

In the 1960s, another important task of adjudication boards was to adjudicate in misdemeanours against road safety. In 1961, in response to the emerging phenomenon of “road hooligans”, the communist authorities introduced a new act, called the Act on Safety and Public Order in Road Traffic on Public Roads.⁹ This Act provided the adjudication boards with new measures consistent with a stronger policy against traffic hooligans. The maximum fines were increased three times and, in case of driving under influence of alcohol, the adjudication boards could retain the drivers’ licenses for some time. The largest part of the adjudication boards activities was concentrated on petty traffic offences committed after the use the alcohol (Łysko, 2012:340-341).

⁹ Ustawa z dnia 27 listopada 1961 r. o bezpieczeństwie i porządku ruchu na drogach publicznych (The Act on Safety and Public Order in Road Traffic on Public Roads), *Dziennik Ustaw*, 1961/53.

5. Repressing the political opponents

At the end of the 1960s, adjudication in petty offences was for the first time used to repress people who openly opposed or expressed objections to the policy of the communist authorities. In Warsaw, adjudication boards punished the participants of students' protests of March 1968, who demanded from the government to limit censorship and widen cultural and artistic freedoms. The students were treated as hooligans, charged with infringement of public peace and order, and their cases were adjudicated in expedite proceedings. Treating political offences as hooliganism was the ground for a rapid decision and immediate enforcement of detention or high fines as a substitute for detention (Ministry of Internal Affairs II, 1968: 10).¹⁰ The practice of punishing offences of political character, which started in March 1968, continued in the 1970s and the 1980s, when fully collaborative adjudication boards were used to repress the opponents of the communist authorities. Such practice was possible because the adjudication boards were composed of people who fully collaborated with the communist authorities (Łysko, 2020: 78-79).

The greatest extent of political repression took place in the 1980s, especially during the period of Martial law (December 1981 – July 1983). Introduced by communist authorities on 13 December 1981, Martial law was the basis for the persecution of activists from the outlawed Solidarity social movement. In the period between 13 December 1981 and 31 December 1982, the adjudication boards punished over 223,000 individuals for violations of the Martial law restrictions. The factual circumstances of committed offenses were primarily administrative in nature as they involved minor violations, such as breaches the curfew/police hours or lack of identification documents in public places (Łysko, 2019: 86-88). Requests (motions) for punishing individuals for offenses which involved openly expressing opposition to the policies of the communist authorities or showing support for the underground Solidarity movement were less frequent. The Ministry of Internal Affairs classified such offences as political cases and ordered the adjudication boards to vigorously repress all manifestations of social resistance. Harsh penalties were imposed even for raising a hand in a “V” (victory) sign or wearing a tiny Solidarity badge (Kolegia, 1987: 17-18).

The repressive character of adjudication in these “political” cases aimed to intimidate the society and ensure the population’s compliance with the com-

¹⁰ Informacja nr 1/68 z przebiegu rozpraw karno-administracyjnych przeciwko uczestnikom zajęć na terenie Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego i niektórych ulic w dniu 8 marca 1968 r., Ministry of Internal Affairs II, sign. 5297 (1968).

munist regime. Misdemeanours such as participation in strikes, street demonstrations or protest actions were typically handled in expedite proceedings and usually punished with detention or high fines, which were often converted into substitute custodial penalty. During the Martial law period, substitute custodial penalty was applied so frequently that the Ministry of Internal Affairs noted more than a two-time increase in its use by the end of 1982. The tendency to abuse preventive detention, which began during the Martial law period, continued throughout the 1980s. The use of substitute custodial penalty expanded so rapidly that, in 1985, the Ministry of Internal Affairs stopped publishing statistics on the number of fines converted into substitute custodial penalty (Szumski, 1993: 113).

In 1986, several petty political offences (such as illegal printing and distribution of critical information), were designated as misdemeanours. In order to eliminate political opposition, it was vital to refer the cases involving illegal printing and distribution of informative materials, publications including criticism on the system and policy of the communist authorities to the boards in charge of adjudicating minor/petty offences. The punishment provided for the commission of these acts was forfeiture of assets, which often included forfeiture of cars or video equipment. It was the consequence of interpreting guidelines contrary to the essence of punishment in the law on petty offences. As the assets subjected to forfeiture were of a value more than ten times higher than the maximum fine, the forfeiture of asset came close to the punishment of confiscation of assets (Szumski, 1995: 164-165).

6. Expedite proceedings in petty offences cases

In cases of petty offences committed by the participants of public protests against the regime's policies and persons regarded by authorities as the opponents of the communist system, sentences were usually passed in the expedite (urgent) proceedings. This special mode of proceedings was initially introduced for the purpose of imposing severe penalties for hooligans, but expedite proceedings were also used for adjudicating another group of people who in the opinion of authorities had a negative attitude to the existing socialist society principles of community life and did not complete the constitutional obligation to work. Expedite proceedings were always used when the accused offender belonged to the so-called social margin group (prostitutes, beggars, vagrants), particularly if they did not have a permanent place of residence, regular employment, or were unemployed. The practice of applying this exceptional mode of penal-administrative proceeding started in the 1960s, when it was introduced in order to punish the perpetrators of "alcoholism and hooliganism-related" offences (Łysko, 2019: 532).

The basic assumption of expedite proceedings was the need for speed, which resulted in deviations from the general procedural principles in misdemeanours cases. These deviations occurred even at the stage of initiating the proceeding, as the Misdemeanour Code (1971) stipulated that the necessary condition for expedite proceedings was “the apprehension of the perpetrator in the act or immediately thereafter”. The consequence of apprehending the perpetrators was their detention and compulsory escort by the People’s Militia to the hearing before the adjudication board (Łysko, 2015: 210-211). After bringing the detained perpetrator before the adjudication board, the People’s Militia officer would submit a motion for punishment which could be submitted orally for the record, which was contrary to the principle of filing a written submission that was applicable in regular criminal proceedings. Then, the chairman of adjudication board was to refer the case for immediate review by the designated adjudication panel. By contrast, in the regular criminal procedure, there was a requirement to notify the accused of the date and place of the hearing at least 7 days in advance (Łysko, 2020: 78-79).

In the expedite proceedings, the emphasis on the speed of proceedings limited the accused person’s right to defense. A person caught in the act of committing the criminal offence was immediately brought before the adjudication board and had no time and opportunity to choose a defense lawyer. Motions submitted by the accused were consistently rejected by the adjudicating boards, which issued penalties solely based on the evidence presented in the motion for punishment (Kolegia, 1987: 15-16).

The sentences passed in expedite proceedings were based on the evidence provided by public prosecutors. Typically, this evidence included written reports or testimonies of People’s Militia officers involved in the apprehension of the offender. Unlike criminal trials, proceeding in misdemeanours cases allowed for deviations from the principle of immediacy, such as the reading of witness interrogation protocols. The justification for using this approach was the conviction that there was no need for direct examination of the evidence. In the case of People’s Militia officers involved in the arrest, the justification was the fact that they were performing important official duties (Kolegia, 1987: 18).

7. The Misdemeanours Code of 1971

The practice of imposing severe punishment for hooligans and political opponents, created as the result of the codification works during 1960-1971, demonstrated the very repressive nature of the substantive misdemeanour

law system in the People's Republic of Poland. The Ministry of Internal Affairs had the decisive impact on the misdemeanour law codification, which was perceived as a tool to "protect the public order and maintain social discipline" (Szumski, 1993: 131). The final result of codification works was the Misdemeanours Code, enacted in 1971;¹¹ after the fall of the communist system, it was subject to some minor amendments and it is still in force today. The Code included "rigorous provisions" on the treatment of people who were perceived as a burden to the society, particularly repeat offenders and hooligans.¹² In the 1971 Code, the hooliganism-related nature of a criminal offence was treated as an aggravating circumstance. The Code introduced several further restrictions for the perpetrators of these offences, including some which had not been part of the legislation at that time: no suspended detention sentence, a total prohibition on issuing a reprimand, and a possibility to impose a fine in case of damage caused by a hooliganism-related act. New anti-hooliganism regulations were accompanied by restrictive penalties which were imposed in case the act was committed under the influence of alcohol. It legitimised the practice of classifying intoxication as the basic premise of a hooliganism-related nature of the act (Marek, 1995: 55).

In the general part of the Misdemeanours Code, almost all new legal provisions were introduced in the spirit of intensifying penalisation. Most of those solutions were created in order to ensure severe punishment for the perpetrators of 'alcoholism and hooliganism-related' offences, who were the most numerous group of offenders. The 1971 Code envisaged many possibilities for more lenient reactions and did not oblige the adjudication bodies to implement harsh legislative policy; however, from the standpoint of judicial practice, it was a continuation of punitive legislative tendencies. The Ministry of Internal Affairs had a decisive impact on the complex misdemeanour law codification, which was perceived as a tool to 'protect public order and maintain social discipline' (Szumski, 1993: 131).

As the general part of the Misdemeanours Code included some provisions that supported a more lenient criminal policy, the provisions in the subject-specific part of the Code included more severe policy. While choosing sanctions for the subject-specific misdemeanours, the legislator primarily

¹¹ Ustawa z dnia 20 maja 1971 r. przepisy wprowadzające Kodeks wykroczeń. (Act of 20 May 1971- Petty Offences Code, *Dziennik Ustaw*, 1971/12).

¹² Tezy wystąpienia Ministra Spraw Wewnętrznych Kazimierza Światały, *Zagadnienia Karno-Administracyjne* (Theses of the speech by the Minister of Internal Affairs Kazimierz Światały, Criminal and Administrative Law Issues), 2. 1- 4. (1970).

focused on the general prevention. As a result, the 1971 Code envisaged widely used traditional penalties of custodial and property-related character. The repressive nature of the subject-specific provisions in the special part of the Code could not be eased even by the general provision on the distinctive character of detention. That solution should be seen as a propaganda declaration that was to hide the fact of a common use of that most severe of principal penalties. Nearly every third misdemeanour from the specific part of the Misdemeanours Code was punishable by detention, which was nearly always imposed in its maximum term (Gubiński, 1972: 8). The detention could be imposed as a consequence of executing a conditionally suspended detention sentence, evasion of the execution of restriction of personal liberty, and especially the execution of an substitute custodial penalty in case of failure to pay the imposed fine. The common use of detention as a peculiar “reinforcement of penal measures” made Polish misdemeanour law one of the most repressive systems in the world. In practise, there was no rational explanation for the frequent use of detention for misdemeanours against public order. The Misdemeanours Code also provided for the use of detention against traffic offenders, people begging in a public place, or women prostituting themselves in public places (Skupiński, 1981: 5).

The provision from the subject-specific part of the 1971 Code which penalises the most common cases of infringement of public peace and order (Art. 51 Misdemeanours Code) was created to implement party authorities’ guidelines which demanded to “fight negative social phenomena definitely and consistently”. The general wording and ambiguous attributes of a criminal offence were accompanied by an extremely wide scope of punishment, which included penalties for inciting, aiding and abetting the infringement of public peace and order (Łysko, 2016: 318). The provision undermining the guaranteed function of criminal law was validly defined by the famous Polish lawyer and scientist L. Falandysz as “a little criminal code” formulated in three sentences. The provision of Misdemeanours Code on penalties for the infringement of public peace and order was introduced not only for the “alcoholism and hooliganism-related” offenders but it was also used in determining the criminal liability of persons accused of alcohol abuse (Łysko, 2019: 229).

The provision which was particularly criticised by academics and legal practitioners was the penalty for public prostitution. This provision was assessed as contradictory to the *nullum crimen sine lege* principle (Falandysz, 1970: 709). Penalisation of prostitution fits the atmosphere of creating artificial compensatory problems, which was typical for the People’s Poland period. The publicising of such problems was to reverse the attention of the society

from the real problems and flaws in the system by creating a negative picture of specific social groups, which were accused by the authorities of disregard for generally imposed rules of conduct and principles of socialist morality. Generally, the subject-specific provisions were used not only against alcoholism and hooliganism-related offenders but also served to repress the political opponents of communist authorities and people belonging to the social margin groups (Łysko, 2016: 318-319).

8. Conclusion

The misdemeanour law system in the People's Republic of Poland covered not only minor infringements of public order but also offences against public peace and order sanctioned with severe penalties. Officially, the substantive provisions of misdemeanor law, as well as the procedural rules and those concerning the organization of adjudicating bodies, were aimed at imposing strict penalties on perpetrators of socially dangerous acts of hooliganism, typically committed under the influence of alcohol. In judicial practice, however, the "hooligan" label was often attached to political opponents of the communist regime and to members of the so-called social margin groups who refused to live in accordance with the top-down moral norms imposed by the authoritarian state. The communist authorities viewed penal-administrative repression not merely as a tool for punishing violations of public order but also as a means of intimidating society and addressing social problems stemming from poorly implemented social policies and years of neglect in youth education and upbringing (Szumski, 1995: 211).

During the entire period, the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Peoples' Republic of Poland supervised the adjudication in petty offences cases, demonstrating an ambition to institute a peculiar ministerial by-law in this area, to repress the society and enforce subordination to state authorities. Based on the Ministry initiative, the 1971 Misdemeanours Code introduced some solutions that supported treating adjudication boards as an instrument for exercising the Ministry interests. Those solutions were particularly used during political crises (Szumski, 1995: 210). The most important was the notion of an alcoholism and hooliganism-related misdemeanour, where the state of intoxication was treated as a decisive circumstance for deciding on a hooligan nature of the crime.

Another basis for the persecution of politic opponents of the communist regime and individuals who were negatively perceived by the authorities were the provisions on penal-administrative proceedings, especially the expedite (urgent) proceedings. Despite their exceptional nature, expedite

proceedings were widely applied in the People's Republic of Poland. The inclusion of all offenses committed by individuals leading the so-called “parasitic lifestyle” and itinerant “bluebirds”¹³ in expedite proceedings constituted part of the communist authorities’ campaign aimed at combating negative social phenomena.

Generally, in penal-administrative proceedings, the function of a public prosecutor was held by officers of the People’s Militia, which was subordinated to the Ministry of Internal Affairs. The Ministry of Internal Affairs controlled the work of bodies that submitted punishment proposals as well as the work of the boards adjudicating petty offences. As a result, the persons accused of committing petty offences of political nature or alcoholism/hooliganism-related character were at a disadvantage. The perpetrators of misdemeanours were in a significantly worse situation in cases they were subjected to expedite proceedings; in such proceedings, the accused person was deprived of the basic human rights’ guarantees (Kolegia, 1987: 1-2). The practice of misusing expedite proceedings as a tool for repressing political opponents was discontinued only in the wake of the socio-political transformations of 1989, and was first manifested in the abolition of the immediate enforcement of judgments issued under this procedure. The possibility of instituting the expedite proceeding was limited to strictly defined cases, and the procedural position of the defendant in this special kind of procedure was significantly strengthened.

In the aftermath of the socio-political breakthrough in 1989, the next step towards liberalising the adjudication in petty offences was discontinuation of adjudicating cases involving political misdemeanours. After the collapse of the communist system, the prosecution of such offences was suspended. The departure from the political intervention in judicial practice was facilitated by the reform in 1990, under which the entire process of adjudication in petty offences (including the judgments on detention) was subjected to judicial review. The institution of general guidelines on penalty policy was abolished. Adjudication boards were removed from the organizational structure of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and placed within the structure of the Ministry of Justice. Their case-law practice no longer supports the administrative policy of the state, nor is it used in adjudicating in petty offences

¹³ “Bluebirds” were the young people who did not want to work and had illegal occupation, such as currency exchange, smuggling, trading at the black markets, etc. They had good incomes from the illegal activities and were rich in comparison to ordinary people who had legal jobs. They often had to change their place of residence because they were persecuted by the communist authorities.

cases. When adjudication boards were transferred to the Ministry of Justice, it suddenly turned out that the provisions of the Misdemeanours Code included conditions for establishing a rational criminal policy. Thus, the process of defusing the repressive adjudication in petty offences started in 1990 (Stachowiak, 2004: 231-214). Adjudication boards were abolished in 2001, when the adjudication in petty offences was vested in criminal courts as a form of administration of justice.

References

- Bafia J. (1959). *O zaostrzeniu i przyśpieszeniu odpowiedzialności karnej za chuligaństwo*. Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Prawnicze
- Falandysz L. (1970). Wykroczenia przeciwko porządkowi i spokojowi publicznemu. *Państwo i Prawo*. 11. 702-718.
- Gubiński A. (1977). Ewolucja stosowanych przez kolegia środków karnych i zasad wymiaru kary. *Zagadnienia Wykroczeń*. 6. 22-39.
- Gubiński A. (1972). Wokół problemów nowej kodyfikacji, *Zagadnienia Wykroczeń*. 3. 2-21.
- Jakubowska-Hara J. (2004). *Grzywna w polskim prawie wykroczeń. Model ustawowy i praktyka*. Warszawa: Europejska Wyższa Szkoła Prawa i Administracji
- Kaliński J. (1995). *Gospodarka Polski w latach 1944 – 1989. Przemiany strukturalne*. Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Ekonomiczne
- Kolegia ds. wykroczeń w PRL. Rozwiązania ustawowe i praktyka (1987). Warszawa-Kraków: Komisja Interwencji i Praworządności NSZZ „Solidarność” oraz Małopolski Komitet Walki o Praworządność
- Łysko M. (2020). Adjudicating in Petty Offences relating to the Compulsory Delivery of Agricultural Products in the Polish People's Republic. In: *Luts-Sootak M., Schäfer F. (ed.), Law and Economics in Urban and Rural Environment. 9th Conference in Legal History in the Baltic Sea Area 16.-20. Mai 2018 in Tallinn, Sagadi und Tartu, Estonia (pp. 203-210)*. Berlin: Peter Lang Verlag
- Łysko M. (2019). Działalność kolegiów do spraw wykroczeń w okresie obowiązywania stanu wojennego. *Studia Prawno-Ekonomiczne*. CXII. 83-89.
- Łysko M. (2018). Ewolucja systemu polskiego prawa wykroczeń w XX w., *Miscellanea Historico-luridica*. XVII (1). 167-192.

Łysko M. (2019). The Influence of Political Factors on the Adjudicating on Petty Offences in the People’s Republic of Poland. In: M. V. Ambrosini V. (ed.), *Historia del derecho*. 73. 527-535.

Łysko M. (2008). Kara pracy poprawczej w orzecznictwie karno-administracyjnym Polski Ludowej. *Miscellanea Historico-Iuridica*. VI. 143-168.

Łysko M. (2020). Karanie uczestników wydarzeń marcowych 1968 r. przez kolegia karno-administracyjne. *Krakowskie Studia z Historii Państwa i Prawa*. 13 (1). 61-81.

Łysko M. (2012). Kształtowanie się ustroju kolegiów orzekających w Polsce Ludowej (1952-1956), *Czasopismo Prawno-Historyczne*. LXIV (2). 249-275.

Łysko M. (2019). Main Problems of the Codification Works on Substantive Misdemeanor Law in People’s Poland, *Studia Iuridica*. LXXX (80). 223-233.

Łysko M. (2015). Obwiniony jako uczestnik postępowania w sprawach o wykroczenia – wczoraj i dziś. In *Gil D., Kruk E. (ed.), Role uczestników postępowań sądowych – wczoraj, dziś, jutro (pp. 199 – 214)*. Lublin: Wydawnictwo UMCS

Łysko M. (2011). Orzecznictwo karno-administracyjne w walce z alkoholizmem w okresie gomułkowskim. *Z dziejów Prawa*. 4. 249-279.

Łysko M. (2009). Orzecznictwo karno-administracyjne w zakresie dostaw obowiązkowych płodów rolnych w Polsce Ludowej. *Miscellanea Historico-Iuridica*. VIII. 189-222.

Łysko M. (2014). Polityczne uwarunkowania orzecznictwa karno-administracyjnego Polski Ludowej, *Studia z dziejów Państwa i Prawa Polskiego*. XVII. 211-232.

Łysko M. (2016). Prace and kodyfikacją materialnego prawa wykroczeń w Polsce Ludowej. Białystok, Wydawnictwo Temida 2.

Łysko M. (2020). Prawo wykroczeń Polski Ludowej. Białystok, Wydawnictwo Temida 2.

Łysko M. (2008). Problem chuligaństwa w orzecznictwie karno-administracyjnym Polski Ludowej (1952-1989). *Czasopismo Prawno-Historyczne*. LX (2). 179-202.

Łysko M. (2011). Przełom roku 1956 w Polsce a orzecznictwo karno-administracyjne, *Zeszyty Prawnicze UKSW*. 11 (4). 277-305.

Łysko M. (2014). Reforma prawa karno-administracyjnego Polski Ludowej z 1958 r., *Z dziejów Prawa*. 7. 211-242.

Łysko M. (2013). Socjalistyczna reforma orzecznictwa karno-administracyjnego Polski Ludowej. In *Gaca A. (ed.), Pro memoriał. Księga pamiątkowa dla uczczenia pamięci Profesor Krystyny Kamińskiej (pp. 315-344)*. Toruń: Wydawnictwo UMK

Łysko M. (2009). System kar w prawie wykroczeń Polski Ludowej. In: *Mikuła M. (ed.), Culpa et poena – z dziejów prawa karnego (pp. 307-326)*. Kraków: Wydawnictwo UJ

Łysko M. (2013). Środki zaskarżania orzeczeń karno-administracyjnych w Polsce Ludowej. In *Gil D. (ed.), Szczególne środki zaskarżenia w ujęciu komparatystycznym (pp. 359-374)*. Stalowa Wola: Wydawnictwo UMCS

Łysko M. (2012). Wykroczenia drogowe w praktyce orzecznictwa karno-administracyjnego okresu gomułkowskiego. *Miscellanea Historico-Juridica*. XI. 315-349.

Marek A. (1975). *Prawo wykroczeń w zarysie*. Warszawa: Państwowe Wydawnictwo Naukowe

Skupiński J. (1981). Kierunki doskonalenia polskiego prawa wykroczeń. *Studia Prawnicze*. 4. 1-25.

Stachowiak S. (2004). Ewolucja polskiego systemu postępowania w sprawach o wykroczenia. In: *Januszewski B. (ed.), Nauka wobec współczesnych zagadnień prawa karnego w Polsce. Księga pamiątkowa Profesora Aleksandra Tobisa (pp. 201-225)*. Poznań: Wydawnictwo Poznańskie

Szumski J. (1993). Główne kierunki polityki karnej realizowanej przez kolegia do spraw wykroczeń w latach 1972 – 1989. *Archiwum Kryminologii*. XIX. 125-146.

Szumski J. (1995). Środki penalne w polskim prawie wykroczeń na tle doświadczeń praktyki. Lublin: Wydawnictwo UMCS

Ministerstwo Spraw Wewnętrznych. (1960). Wytoczne Ministra Spraw Wewnętrznych w zakresie orzecznictwa karno-administracyjnego na rok 1960. Poradnik dla Kolegiów Orzekających (Guidelines of the Minister of Internal Affairs on criminal-administrative jurisprudence for 1960, Guide for Adjudication Boards, Ministry of Internal Affairs). 2. 1-5. (1960)

Tezy wystąpienia Ministra Spraw Wewnętrznych Kazimierza Światały, *Zagadnienia Karno-Administracyjne* (Theses of the speech by the Minister of Internal Affairs Kazimierz Światała, Criminal and Administrative Law Issues), 2. 1-4. (1970)

Legal acts

Ustawa o orzecznictwie karno-administracyjnym (The Act on the Criminal and Administrative Jurisprudence), *Dziennik Ustaw*, 1951/66, item 454.

Ustawa o zaostrzeniu odpowiedzialności karnej za chuligaństwo (Act on Increasing Criminal Responsibility for Hooliganism), *Dziennik Ustaw*, 1958/34, item 152.

Ustawa z dnia 2 grudnia 1958 r. o zmianie ustawy z dnia 15 grudnia 1951 r. o orzecznictwie karno-administracyjnym (the Act amending the Act on Criminal and Administrative Jurisprudence of 15th December 1951), *Dziennik Ustaw*, 1958/77, item 396.

Ustawa z dnia 10 grudnia 1959 r. o zwalczaniu alkoholizmu (Act on Combating Alcoholism), *Dziennik Ustaw*, 1959/69, item 434.

Ustawa z dnia 27 listopada 1961 r. o bezpieczeństwie i porządku ruchu na drogach publicznych (Act on Safety and Public Order in Road Traffic on Public Roads), *Dziennik Ustaw*, 1961/53, item 295.

Ustawa z dnia 20 maja 1971 r. przepisy wprowadzające Kodeks wykroczeń (Act of 20 May 1971- Petty Offences Code, *Dziennik Ustaw*, 1971/12, item 114.

Documents from the archives of the Institute of National Remembrance in Warsaw

Analiza orzecznictwa karno-administracyjnego za okres IV kwartału 1954 r. z terenu województwa łódzkiego, Ministry of Internal Affairs I, sign. 526 (1954)

Analiza udziału orzecznictwa karno-administracyjnego w 1955 roku w realizacji planów dostaw obowiązkowych, Ministry of Internal Affairs I, sign. 11 + 2 (1955).

Notatka informacyjna dla Kolegium Ministerstwa Spraw Wewnętrznych o przebiegu orzecznictwa karno-administracyjnego w 1955 roku, Ministry of Internal Affairs II, sign. 6443 (1955)

Informacja nr 1/68 z przebiegu rozpraw karno-administracyjnych przeciwko uczestnikom zajęć na terenie Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego i niektórych ulic w dniu 8 marca 1968 r., Ministry of Internal Affairs II, sign. 5297 (1968)

Prof. dr iur. hab. Marcin Łysko,

Ванредни професор,
Правни факултет, Универзитет у Бјалистоку,
Република Пољска

**СУЂЕЊЕ ЗА СИТНЕ ПРЕКРШАЈЕ У НАРОДНОЈ РЕПУБЛИЦИ ПОЉСКОЈ У
КОНТЕКСТУ ДРУШТВЕНО-ПОЛИТИЧКИХ ПРОБЛЕМА У ПОСЛЕРАТНОМ
ПЕРИОДУ**

Резиме

У Народној Републици Пољској (1944-1989), суђење за ситне прекршаје коришћено је као инструмент репресије против људи који су сматрани противницима комунистичког система, и као средство решавања друштвено-политичких проблема насталих деморализацијом друштва, изазваном Другим светским ратом и неуспесима у области друштвеног васпитања младих. Најозбиљнији друштвени проблем у то време био је хулиганизам, па су против бројних учинилаца ових дела коришћене репресивне мере административно-казненог карактера. Ознака „хулиган“ често се везивала за политичке противнике комунистичког режима и припаднике друштвено-маргиналних група који су одбијали да живе у складу са моралним нормама наметнутих од стране ауторитарне комунистичке државе. Учинιοци ових кривичних дела врло често били су хронични алкохоричари или особе под утицајем алкохола, па је у административној пракси настао термин „прекршаји повезани са алкохолизмом и хулиганизмом“. Прекршајна већа која су поступала у случајевима ове врсте била су под ингеренцијом Министарства унутрашњих послова. Прекршајна већа су истовремено служила као инструмент репресије не само против политичких противника, већ и против чланова такозваних друштвено-маргиналних група, јер закон није предвиђао казне за проституцију, просјачење, беспосличарење и бескућништво. Широки обим примене убрзаног поступка био је још један основ за прогон политичких неистомишљеника и појединаца из непожељних социјалних категорија од стране власти. У овим поступцима, прекршајна већа су изрицала строге новчане казне. У случају неплаћања, новчане казне су одмах замењиване казном притвора. У убрзаном поступку, починиоци ових дела били су у знатно горем положају него у редовном поступку, јер нису поштоване основне гаранције права окривљеног. Практика поступања прекршајних већа за ситне прекршаје престала је да се користи као инструмент за сузбијање политичке опозиције и реша-

вање друштвених проблема тек након друштвено-политичког преокрета 1989. године.

Кључне речи: *прекршајна већа за ситне прекршаје, Народна Република Пољска, Закон о прекршајима, прекршаји „повезани са алкохолом и хулиганством”, убрзани поступак.*

СЕСИЈА ЗА ЕКОНОМИЈУ, ФИНАНСИЈСКО И ТРГОВИНСКО ПРАВО

ECONOMIC, FINANCIAL AND TRADE LAW SESSION

